

Complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with Benzimidazole and 2-Methylbenzimidazole

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Complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with benzimidazole (BzH) and 2-methylbenzimidazole (MBzH) of formulae $[ML_2]$ ($M=Zn^{2+}$, Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} and $LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$), $[Cd(LH)_2X_2]$, ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$ and $X=Cl^-$ or NCS^-), $[Zn(BzH)_4]SO_4 \cdot H_2O$, $[Hg(LH)Cl_2]$ ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$) and $[Hg(Bz)Cl]$ have been prepared and characterised by electrical conductivity measurement and ir spectral data.

In previous communications the complexes of benzimidazole (BzH), 2-methylbenzimidazole (MBzH) and substituted benzimidazoles with a number of transition metal ions have been reported¹⁻⁶. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with BzH and MBzH.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by reported method^{7,8}. Metal salts and solvents used were of E. Merck extra pure, or BDH AnalaR quality.

Preparation of complexes: $[ML_2]$, ($M=Zn^{2+}$, Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} and $LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$): An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal acetate (0.01 mole in 100 ml 50% ethanol) was treated with 2% ethanolic solution of ligand in excess (1 : 2.5 molar ratio). The pH of the resulting solution was raised to 7-9 in case of benzimidazole and between 9 and 11 in case of 2-methylbenzimidazole by adding dilute ammonia, when *bis* chelated neutral complexes separated. The products were digested on a steam bath and filtered hot. The complexes were washed with ethanol and dried in an air oven at 110°.

$[Cd(LH)_2X_2]$, ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$ and $X=Cl^-$ or NCS^-): Methanolic solution of appropriate metal salt (0.01 mole in 50 ml) was treated with stoichiometric proportion of ligand dissolved in hot methanol. The diacido complexes separated either on standing or concentrating the solutions to a small volume. The products were collected on a filter, washed with methanol, dry ether and dried *in vacuo* over $CaCl_2$.

$[Zn(BzH)_4]SO_4 \cdot H_2O$: An aqueous methanolic solution of hydrated zinc sulphate (1.5 g in 5 ml water and 30 ml methanol) was treated with 2.5 g ligand dissolved in hot methanol. The resulting solution was concentrated and treated with an excess of ether when complex sulphate separated immediately. The product was filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

$[Hg(LH)Cl_2]$, ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$): Methanolic solution of mercuric chloride (0.01 mole in 30 ml) was treated with molar proportion of ligand dissolved in methanol when cream coloured precipitate separated immediately. The products were filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo*.

$[Hg(Bz)Cl]$: About 2 g of $Hg(BzH)Cl_2$ was suspended in aqueous ethanol and refluxed on a steam bath for about 1 hr, when a cream coloured insoluble precipitate was obtained. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

The results of elemental analysis and molar electrical conductance values of the complexes at room temperature are recorded in Table I. The molar electrical conductance measurements and ir spectra of the complexes as KBr disc or Nujol mull were recorded as reported earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Depending on the pH of the reaction medium BzH and MBzH coordinate as neutral as well as mono anionic ligands and form *bis* ligated inner complexes $[ML_2]$, ($M=Zn^{2+}$, Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} and $LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$) and acido complexes $[Cd(LH)_2X_2]$, ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$ and $X=Cl^-$ or NCS^-), $[Zn(BzH)_4]SO_4 \cdot H_2O$, $[Hg(LH)Cl_2]$ ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$) and $[Hg(Bz)Cl]$. The *bis* ligated inner complexes ML_2 and $[Hg(Bz)Cl]$ are insoluble in water, ethanol, benzene, etc. but sparingly soluble in DMF on warming. The insolubility of these complexes indicate their polymeric nature.

The diacido complexes $[Cd(LH)_2X_2]$ ($LH=BzH$ or $MBzH$ and $X=Cl^-$ or NCS^-) are slightly soluble in ethanol and methanol but dissolve appreciably in DMF and DMSO. The DMF solution of the complexes shows small electrical conductance value ($\Lambda_M=20-35 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) indicating that anions are coordinated to metal atom. A small molar conductance value of these complexes can be attributed to solvation in DMF solution. The

TABLE I

Compound	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)			$\Delta\lambda$ mol ⁻¹ ohm ⁻¹ cm ² (in DMF)
	Metal	Nitrogen	Halogen/ Sulphate	
[Zn(Bz) ₂]	21.61 (21.83)	18.41 (18.71)	—	5
[Cd(Bz) ₂]	31.81 (31.45)	16.01 (16.17)	—	7
[Hg(Bz) ₂]	45.61 (46.30)	12.81 (12.85)	—	6
[Zn(MBz) ₂]	20.21 (19.96)	16.91 (17.11)	—	7
[Cd(MBz) ₂]	29.81 (30.02)	14.68 (14.96)	—	8
[Hg(MBz) ₂]	43.01 (43.40)	11.81 (12.12)	—	6
[Hg(BzH)Cl ₂]	51.12 (51.64)	10.51 (10.81)	17.81 (18.19)	—
[Hg(Bz)Cl]	57.11 (56.80)	8.01 (7.93)	9.76 (10.07)	—
[Hg(MBzH)Cl ₂]	47.91 (48.16)	10.21 (10.09)	17.21 (17.02)	—
[Zn(BzH) ₄]SO ₄ .H ₂ O	10.32 (10.04)	17.31 (17.19)	14.88 (14.73)	122
[Cd(BzH) ₂ Cl ₂]	26.11 (26.81)	13.21 (13.36)	16.61 (16.91)	24
[Cd(BzH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	24.45 (24.25)	18.11 (17.92)	—	34
[Cd(MBzH) ₂ Cl ₂]	25.41 (25.12)	12.34 (12.52)	16.11 (15.85)	35
[Cd(MBzH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	23.10 (22.83)	17.21 (17.07)	—	26

molar electrical conductance value of [Zn(BzH)₄].SO₄.H₂O in DMF ($\Lambda_M=122$ ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ cm²) indicates the ionic nature of sulphate group⁹ in DMF solution.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of BzH and MBzH display (N-H) stretching band at 3248 and 3218 cm⁻¹, respectively. In acido complexes Cd(LH)₂X₂, the (N-H) stretching band is not affected appreciably but disappears in neutral inner complexes [ML₂] (M=Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or Hg²⁺ and LH=BzH or MBzH). In case of [Hg(BzH)Cl₂] the (N-H) stretch is observed at 3120 cm⁻¹ indicating that imidazole NH is involved in bonding. The (C=N) vibration of BzH and MBzH, observed at 1600 and 1596 cm⁻¹, respectively, is shifted to higher frequencies by 8-22 cm⁻¹ indicating that imidazole ring tertiary nitrogen is involved in bonding in these complexes¹⁰. The (N-H) deformation vibration of BzH (1492 cm⁻¹) and 2-methylbenzimidazole (1482 cm⁻¹) is not affected appreciably in [Cd(LH)₂X₂] and [Zn(BzH)₄]SO₄.H₂O

but shifted to higher frequency in [Hg(BzH)Cl₂] by 12 cm⁻¹. In bis ligated neutral complexes the (N-H) deformation vibration almost disappears indicating the deprotonation of NH hydrogen.

The ir spectra of [Cd(LH)₂(NCS)₂] (LH=BzH or MBzH) display (C≡N) stretch at 2095±5 cm⁻¹ as broad and very strong band and (C=S) at 840±5 cm⁻¹ as weak band. The broadness of (C≡N) vibration is taken as characteristic of N-bonded thiocyanate group in complexes¹¹. The ir spectrum of [Zn(BzH)₄]SO₄.H₂O displays a broad and strong (SO) vibration at 1135 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) and no splitting of this band could be detected indicating that sulphate is ionic in complex [Zn(BzH)₄]SO₄.H₂O. A broad band at 3450 cm⁻¹ and a weak band at 830 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the presence of lattice or coordinated water molecule in the complex¹¹. From stoichiometry and ir spectral studies, four coordinated tetrahedral structure is suggested for these Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Hg²⁺ complexes since tetrahedral structure is more preferred geometry for these metal ions¹³.

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